

Continuous Assessment as A Model of Evaluation in Social Studies Classroom in Nigerian Schools

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to find out the place of continuous assessment in academic achievement of students in Nigerian secondary schools, as the introduction was described as motivation for scholars. It is observed that the assessment put forward at the end of the session, term or the course of study has some inherent weaknesses. Therefore, the New National Policy in Education emphasized the use of continuous assessment in schools. The write up looks at the continuous assessment as a model of Evaluation in Social Studies. Recommendations were made.

Keywords: Continuous Assessment, Evaluation, Social Studies,

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Introduction

The setting up of various education commissions to look for a more comprehensive and functional educational policy has been on the increase for long. Notable among these are Phelps-Stokes 1922, Dike 1958, Ashby (1959), Banjo (1960) Taiwo (1961) and Ikoku (1962). All these commission has in one way or the other condemned the old educational system as being more cognitive. To them, more emphasis should be placed on the affective and psychomotor domains rather than cognitive.

Evaluation is the structured interpretation and given of meaning to predict or actual impacts of proposal or results. It looks at original objectives and at what is either predicted or what was accomplished and how it was accomplished. Evaluation can be formative, that is taking place during the development of a concept or proposal, project or organization, with the intentions of improving the value or effectiveness of the proposal, project or organization. It can also be summative, drawing lessons from a completed action or project or an organization at a later point in time or circumstances.

Evaluation is systematic, rigorous and meticulous application of scientific methods to assess the design, implementation, improvement or outcomes of a program. It is a resource intensive process, frequently requiring, resources, such as evaluator expertise, labour, time and a sizeable budget. Evaluation is the process of using both quantitative and qualitative techniques to gather information for decision making. It is also a process of determining the extent to which learning experience have actually produced the desired result.

According to free online dictionary, evaluation is to ascertain or fix the value or worth. To examine and judge carefully, appraise see synonyms estimate. Evaluation is out equivalent to research, though it employs research techniques as a mean of generating the necessary information, and uses similar criteria for the reliability and validity to judge the quality of the evidence. Evaluation is broader than research, as it usually requires information about a range of situations products and processes. This is a subtle difference between evaluation and research, in that evaluation involves making judgment about the value of what is being evaluated. Evaluation in an education setting is the process whereby evidence is being sought that the learning experiences designed for students are effective. It is a qualitative description of the progress being made on the stipulated instructional objectives.

There are different steps towards the evolution of the present policy of education, generally known as the 6-3-3-4 which began in (1969) when the National Educational Research Council (NERC) Conference was a turning point in the Nation's Educational Development. It was quite significant in that the objective of the conference was to review the old goals and identify new national ones at the primary, secondary and tertiary level. This conference serves as the nucleus of the new National Policy on Education. The 1969 curriculum conference has included in its recommendation amongst others, a national philosophy of education, goals of primary education, objectives of secondary education, purposes of tertiary education, role of teacher education, foundations of science and technical education for living, and control of public education. Most of the above recommendations are included in the National Policy of education and adopted by the Federal government. Western method of assessment was introduced in the form of internal and external examination.

Internal are conducted by each school for assessing the progress of its student and such examinations are usually conducted at the end of the school year or usually conducted at the end of every school term and most decisions are based on the raw scores provided by the teachers. The external examinations are conducted by agencies that are external to the pupils in the sense that they have not been responsible for teaching the pupils. Typical examples of

external examinations that operated in our schools systems before the introduction of continuous assessment were: School leaving certificate Examinations, which operated at the primary school level, Teachers Grade two examinations, another external examinations for the secondary school graduates that is still in existence but with modification to reflect the new system is the West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and General Certificate Examination (GCE). The internal and external examinations are independent of one another. The external examination can be done by any student whether within or outside the school system.

Ipaye (1952) noted the following as the weakness of the internal and external examinations, used in making decisions: the assessment is directed mostly to the thought aspect of learning activities, the assessment put emphasis or decision at the end of the year, the term or the end of the course, the marks obtained in different subjects as given by different teachers will not have equal weight and the information provided is usually scanty and all are generated towards the cognitive domain only. It is in line with the problems and weaknesses above that the New National Policy on Education emphasized the use of continuous assessment.

The introduction of continuous assessment into our schools is hailed as long overdue and a welcome development. It is an innovation, not only in social studies, but also in other subjects as well with attendant advantages such as: the abolition of the sixth form course, outright omission of formal examination at the end of the first six years of primary education, as certificates will be based on continuous assessment and the junior secondary school leaving certificate will be based on the state examination and continuous assessment method with certificates issued by the head teacher and though a formal examination will be given at the end of the three year secondary course, performance during the three years will be weighed and taken into account for certification purpose.

As robust as the meaning and content of evaluation presented above, both government owned and private schools, school administrators, policy makers in education in Nigeria, are aware of the significant problems associated with the evaluation of the near policy of continuous assessment for the educational system in general and teachers in particular. Experience has shown that Evaluation in Nigeria schools is faced with problems which may include, the class size, training levels of teachers, shortage of funds, absence of school records, training integrity of teachers.

It appears that teachers in schools face the dilemma as to what guidance he should give the pupils if the completed work is used as evidence of attainment, the rigidity of moderation or otherwise and increasing difficulty of equating standard in any subject.

Experience has shown that most social studies teachers do not participate in maintaining students records in cumulative folder containing personal, home, interest, intelligence, achievement attendance and other data. Evidence abound that Social Studies teachers finding it difficult to interpret test results to parents, other teachers and students whenever this is necessary. It appears that most social studies teachers neglect research studies such as follow up and evaluation studies, community surveys for educational and occupational opportunities for youths and various strategies that are needed for the enhancement of guidance.

Researchers carried out some work on continuous assessment in the past. Most of them hold the view that success in school work in the past can reasonably be expected to give a fairly trends indication of success in school work at a later date. Dempster (2015) expressed the view that the results of test in the basic school subjects are likely to be useful forecast of success in related school subject at later stages.

Famuyibo (2018) on the other hand opined that with average children, amount and accuracy of their present knowledge forms but a rough uncertain index of their power to acquire knowledge. Majemite (2020) concluded that the practicing teachers will do his best to base his assessment of children on combination of factors and the on-going activity of the pupils throughout the year will be one of the yardsticks. Dsakwe (2018) opined that several pupils who are selected as a result of their good performance in entrance and placement examinations failed to reach the scholastic standard of the continuous assessment given to them in schools. He therefore cautioned that continuous assessment should not be used as predictor of performance in success in final and placement examination of students. This research found out the importance of continuous assessment as predictors or otherwise of academic achievement in final and placement examination at students in the secondary schools level in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The importance of evaluation in Nigeria schools cannot be over emphasized. The weaknesses of internal and external examinations used in making decisions such as previous assessment directed mostly to the thought aspect (cognitive learning activities with the emphasis in decision at the end of the year is obvious. Again it is observed that the marks obtained in different subjects as given by different teachers may not have equal weight and the information provided is usually scanty with all tilting towards the cognitive domain only. In view of the problems above, the New National Policy on education emphasized the use of continuous assessment. The introduction of continuous assessment into our schools has been described by scholars as innovative. This is not without problems Experience has shown that lack of qualified Social Studies teachers with most teachers apparently ignorant of the construction and administration of texts, over population in schools, inadequate library and laboratory equipment are some problems experienced.

It is also observed that tests constructed by Social studies teachers for affective and psychomotor domain are scanty. Emphasis is on the cognitive domain. Teacher's attitude towards test construction and administration is negative. Experience has shown that there are differences in the procedures for scoring and grading the various assessment instruments in the various schools. It appears teacher's attitude towards the construction and operation of continuous assessment is not very encouraging. Teachers in most cases consider administration of continuous assessment before the final and placement examination as a weighty assignment which is not worth the efforts. The assessment put on the end of the course, term or session is more favourable for teachers, yet the innovative nature of continuous assessment together with its attendant benefits make it imperative for teachers to implement if issues like class sizes, training integrity of teachers, shortage of funds and absence of school records are to be addressed. The research is in line with the suggestion above.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of carrying out this research was to know the impact of evaluation in social studies classroom. The essence is to found out whether social studies teachers were making use of continuous assessment properly in the teaching and learning paradox and also to examine the place of continuous assessment in formulating social studies objectives. The attitude of teachers towards the construction and implementation of continuous assessment and the problem militating against successful usage of continuous assessment on a model for evaluation in social studies classroom were investigated

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment.
2. There is no significant difference between the strategies and procedure used in schools for continuous assessment and the recommended ones.

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used for the study. This is because it enabled the researcher to have complete collection of relevant data by using validated and reliable questionnaires from larger population without any form of modification.

The population for the study consisted of all the social studies teachers in primary and secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area of Ekiti State. The sample used was 100 teachers drawn from 10 schools in the local government area (5 secondary and 5 primary schools). Purposive and stratified sampling package were used to select the schools from the local government area. Stratified randomly technique was also used to select the teachers used for the study.

The instrument used for the study was a questionnaire designed by the researchers with reference to some social studies textbooks and continuous assessment booklets. The questionnaire was designed to elicit information on the effective evaluation problems of continuous assessment in schools. The subjects were required to indicate on five-point rating scale, their positions and feelings on each of the item on the questionnaire. They were encouraged to give their honest position and feelings concerning continuous assessment in schools. The respondents were assured of the confidentiality of their responses.

The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test-re-test method. Scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis. A reliability coefficient of 0.71 was obtained which was considered an adequate for the study. Inferential statistics (T-test) was used with a level of 0.05 of significance to test the hypotheses.

Results

Table 1: The Relationship between Continuous Assessments in Social Studies and JSCE examination scores

Variables	N	$\sum X, \sum Y$	$\sum X^2, \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r
CA		5903	104530		
(X)				203843	
JSCE	400				0.15
(Y)					
		14024	517146		

Table 1, shows that the correlation coefficient (r) between variables (X) and (Y) is 0.15. The result shows that there was a negative relationship between continuous assessment in social studies and junior secondary school certificate examinations.

Table 2: The Relationship between Continuous Assessment scores in English language and JSCE scores in in English language

Variables	N	$\sum X, \sum Y$	$\sum X^2, \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r
CA		27,82	94163		
(X)				213124	
JSCE	400				0.13
(Y)					
		14860	569018		

The table shows that the calculated correlation coefficient (r) between the two variables (X) and (Y) is 0.13. This shows that the relationship between continuous assessment scores and scores in English language in junior secondary school certificate examination of students in social studies classroom is negative.

Table 3: The relationship between the continuous assessment scores in mathematics and JSCE scores in Mathematics

Variables	N	$\sum X, \sum Y$	$\sum X^2, \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r
CA		2633	84009		
(X)				169707	
JSCE	400				-0.60
(Y)					
		13769	482909		

Table 3 shows that the correlation coefficient calculated (r) between variable (X) and (Y) is -0.60. this means that the relationship between continuous scores in mathematics and score of junior secondary school examination in mathematics is negative.

Table 4: The relationship between the continuous assessment scores in integrated science and the JSCE score in integrated science

Variables	N	$\sum X, \sum Y$	$\sum X^2, \sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r
CA		5766	94798		
(X)				191715	
JSCE	400				-0.01
(Y)					
		13319	486728		

Table 4 shows that the calculated correlation coefficient (r) between variables (X) and (Y) is -0.01. this means that the relationship between the continuous assessment scores in integrated science and the JSCE score is negative.

Hypotheses Testing

Two null hypotheses were tested in this research.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment in schools.

Table 5: t-test analysis showing difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment in schools

Variable	N	X	SA	DF	T-OBS	T-CAL
Male	61	2.52	1.72	1.48	2.65	1.96
Female	98	3.26	1.64			

The first hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment. The five groups based on their score were compared using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significant. For the male teachers the mean scores was 2.52 with 1.72 as standard deviation, for the female, the mean score is on 3.26 with standard deviation of 1.64. The result indicated that there is significant difference between male and female teachers since the t-obs is 2.65 and t-crit is 1.96: the hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the attitude of senior and junior teachers in the administration of continuous assessment

Table 6: t-test analysis showing difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment in schools

Variable	N	X	SA	DF	T-OBS	T-CAL
Senior Teacher	62	4.18	1.21	1.48	4.18	1.96
Junior Teacher	88	3.30	1.30			

From the presentation above, senior teachers had a mean of 4.18 with standard deviation of 1.21. while the junior teacher had a mean of 3.30 with a standard deviation of 1.30. the t-obs value was 4.18 and t-crit value was 1.96. this means that there is a significant difference in the attitude of senior and junior teacher towards continuous assessment.

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis states if there is a significant difference in the attitude of male and female teachers towards continuous assessment. The result above showed that the hypothesis is rejected, that confirmed the findings of Oyerinde and Falayajo (1984) that teachers attitude towards continuous assessment is one of the problems facing the implementation of continuous assessment in schools.

Teachers are not ready to respond to the government policy in continuous assessment. Part of the reason could be the low morale given backlog of salaries arrears and low incentives as a result of being seen and treated as second class citizens. Since teachers attitude and behaviours appear to be important antecedents of teachers effectiveness, the development of the right attitude towards construction and usage of continuous assessment is a step in the right direction.

Hypothesis 2 state that there is no significant difference in the attitude of senior teachers and junior teachers in the administration of continuous assessment, senior teachers had a mean of 4.18 with a standard deviation of 1.21 while the junior teachers had a mean of 3.30 with a standard deviation of 1.30 t-obs value was 4.18 while t-crit was 1.96 at 0.5 level of significance. The analysis above shows that there is a significant difference between the senior teachers and junior teachers attitude in the administration of continuous assessment. The hypothesis is rejected. Junior teachers with indifferent attitude to continuous assessment are less likely to absorb the essence of continuous assessment than the senior teachers that are favourable disposed to it. Ekiugbo (2015) opined that attitude towards any subject is considered as both an input and output variables because such attitude is related to the subject in a way that reinforces higher or lower performance. He argued that attitude is a rather complex phenomenon which develops over time and may not be changed overnight. Close to this is the submission of Famuyibo (2018) that attitude formed through definite intellectual process are not so frequent as those obtained in the other ways. He maintained that being knowledgeable about a phenomenon may not be sufficient predictor of negative or positive disposition towards the object of knowledge hence he cautioned that learners progress in any area of learning only as far as they need in order to achieve their purpose.

Conclusion

The results of this investigation have provided some empirical evidence in support of the need to develop the right attitude towards the construction and implementation of the continuous assessment in Nigeria schools in general and schools in Ekiti state in particular, in respective of the numbers of years on the Job and experience.

Implication of the Study for Social Studies Teachers

The study has shown that mere establishment of social studies programmes in Nigerian schools cannot achieve laudable goals, if social studies teachers who are charged with these duties are not effective in performance of their roles and function. Social studies teachers should develop the right attitude towards the construction and usage of continuous assessment.

In the analysis it was revealed that experience of teachers matters a lot in the construction and usage of continuous assessment. The more experienced teachers are the more painstaking that they can mentor the junior ones on the need and importance of continuous assessment in social studies classroom.

The social studies teachers should participate actively in the school testing programmes and assist in interpreting test results to parents, teachers and students whenever this is necessary

Recommendations

1. The social studies teacher should be in the fore front in organizing disseminating materials of educational, occupational and social personnel nature for the benefits of students, parents and school staff.
2. The social studies teachers should participate actively in research studies such as follow up and evaluation studies, community survey for educational and occupational opportunities for youths and various strategies that are needed for the enhancement of continuous assessment construction and usage.
3. The Social studies teacher should cooperate with other teachers, school authorities and other professionals to popularize the use of continuous assessment in schools.
4. Social studies teachers should encourage positive attitudes and interest of students towards continuous assessment.

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